

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN BRITISH ENGLISH AND AMERICAN IDIOMS

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Abstract: This article is directed to define the necessity of the usage of idioms in the language preserving the main peculiarities of idioms in the English language. The idioms were taken as a more colorful branch of the language and are used to make stronger impression on people. An idiom can have a literal meaning, but its alternate, figurative meaning must be understood metaphorically. A speech form or an expression of a given language that is peculiar to itself grammatically or cannot be understood from the individual meaning of its elements.

Key words: idiomacity, figurative expressions, colorful, fascinating, emotive, stylistic peculiarities.

“An idiom” is a conventionalized expression whose meaning cannot be determined from the meaning of its part. Idioms differ from other figurative expressions, such as similes and metaphors, so they have conventionalized meanings.

Also in this qualification we can find out about how to distinguish idioms from the free word-groups and from phrasemes.

There are some distinctions between the idioms used in British English and the idioms used in American English, although the majority of idioms are common to both varieties.

We covered both British and American idioms in the dictionary and there are variations in form of usage. For example, speakers of British English say that people

take things in their stride, where the speakers of American English say they take things in stride. [2,76]

The situation is complicated because idiom usage changes rapidly, some idioms are not used in American English.

Ex: - “on a sticky wicket” and “calk and cheese” whereas others are rarely used in British English.

Ex: - live high on the hog, spin your wheels

However, many other idioms where originally American have become fashionable in British English in particular in journalism or in the media.

Other American idioms become too unknown to British speakers because of the influence of American culture, for example films and music.

In some cases American idioms are now so common in British English that it would be wrong to label them as only or even mainly-used in American English.

Even though some people may think of these idioms as Americans, they are now much more widely known and used.

As we know idiomacity is the branch of general linguistics which deals with syntactic and expressive stylistic peculiarities of idioms.

It is likely, though certain, that every human language has idioms, and there are a lot of them.

Indeed, many of languages are idiomatic in structure: even the most formal of structures contain characteristics, such as general typology, which categorically distinguish it from other languages.

A typical English commercial idiom dictionary lists about 4000. Catch phrases and bits of slang or jargon are sometimes called idioms.

They are somewhat related, but some people passionately argue that they are not actually idioms.

Native speakers of a language use idioms all the time. Idioms are the grease that make language flow.

Students are often embarrassed and frustrated if they can't understand the idioms which a speaker is using. In some cases, misunderstanding can lead to become one of them to be offended.

Communication is everything! And idioms make our speech colorful, fascinating, emotive and likable.[1,12-14]

A strong knowledge of idioms will help student to be better speakers and negotiators. And they will be in a much better position to take advantage of the opportunities that come to their way.

In examples it is clear that the idiom used as a whole expression. This the traditional view of idioms. But what exactly is an idiom?

This is not an easy question to answer, because many parts of speech may be called idiom. In general, however, an idiom is an expression which has a special meaning and this meaning cannot be understood completely by looking at the individual words in the idiom.

Or an idiom is a phrase which means something different from the meaning of the separate words that are part of it.

If you do not know that the words have special meaning together, you may well misinterpret what someone is saying or be puzzled by why they are saying something that is not true or irrelevant.

Usually it cannot be understood by the literal interpretation of the words that make up the expression used together. The words convey meanings that are often unrelated to the individual words in the idiom.

Some idioms have become so well worn that they are also clichés: overused or commonplace expressions. Some idioms are slang. They may be used to create an effect such as shock, irreverence or exaggeration.

For example, learners might not recognize the idioms like **bite someone's head off** or **out in the cold**. [3]

Then they will have problems in understanding remarks such as don't bite my head off just because you are bad tempered or they were going to play together and that left me out in the cold, you know.

The same process is followed in the Uzbek language also. One may well misunderstand or be puzzled when you say:

Ex: “boshi osmonga yetdi”, “xamirdan qil sug’urganday”, Quloqqa lag’mon ilmoq”, “Qo’ltig’idan tarvuzi tushib ketdi” etc.

Then they will have difficulties in understanding remarks such as:

Ex: Zamira diplomini eson-omon himoya qilib a’lo baho olganiga boshi osmonga yetdi.

Nodira opa o’zining taqdirlanganlar ro’yxatida yo’qligini bilgach tarvuzi qo’ltig’idan tushib ketdi.

Dugonam bu ishni xamirdan qil sug’urganday amalga oshirdiki, hech kim bizni sezmadim ham.

Idioms are typically metaphorical. They are effectively metaphors which have become fixed or fossilized. In some cases, it is fairly easy to know the idiomatic meaning. [4]

Ex: **-kill two birds with one stone**¹ – means to manage to do two things at the same time, instead of just one, because it is convenient to do both and the image in the metaphors supports this meaning. This process in Uzbek is also absorbed for instance:

Ex: - bir o’q bilan ikki quyovni o’ldirmoq.

In other cases the literal meaning may make no sense itself.

Ex: - **move heaven and earth** – literally describes an action which is physically impossible. In a few further cases, the metaphors in the idioms are peculiar and their true origins are unknown so it is very difficult to see how or why the idioms have come to have their current meanings.

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE

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